

THE HISTORY OF THE FORMATION OF LINGUOPOETICS AND ITS PLACE IN THE SYSTEM OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20695594>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 09th June 2026

Accepted: 11th June 2026

Online: 13th June 2026

KEYWORDS

linguopoetics, poetics, rhetoric, aesthetic function of language, literary text, philological analysis, anthropocentric paradigm

ABSTRACT

The article provides a comprehensive analysis of the history of linguopoetics, its role within the system of philology, and the stages of its development as an independent branch. Starting from the philological views of the ancient scholar Aristotle, theories dedicated to studying the aesthetic function of language in Western, Russian, and Uzbek linguistics are comparatively examined. Linguopoetics is evaluated as a field that fills the gaps at the intersection of linguistics and literary studies, thereby ensuring general philological integrity.

Introduction

In world linguistics, numerous fundamental studies on the theoretical aspects of linguopoetics have been conducted by scholars such as V. Vinogradov, G.O. Vinokur, B.A. Larin, and V.M. Zhirmunsky [1]. Emerging in the second half of the 20th century as a result of the shift from structural analysis to anthropocentric research methods, linguopoetics has become one of the most promising fields. Initially studied under the term "language of the literary work," this discipline is recognized today as a specialized branch that thoroughly investigates the system of poetic expressive means that ensure the harmony of form and content in a literary text [5; 7].

Main body and methodology

Linguopoetics was formed at the convergence of linguistics and poetics [8; 9]. The term "poetics" was first used in Aristotle's *Poetics*, which serves as the primary source for establishing linguistic views on the language of literary works [2]. In his work, Aristotle advanced the idea that poetic meaning must be understood through words and language units [2]. Professor A. Nurmonov notes that before linguistics emerged as an independent science, its core issues were studied within philosophy under a general philological approach [3].

In the history of poetics, phenomena related to speech and thought were initially studied within "rhetoric" (the theory of expressive speech that examines effective methods of speech construction). The fundamental roots of modern linguopoetics can be traced back to Aristotle's views on rhetoric [2].

There are also tendencies to interpret this field purely as an object of literary studies. However, as Professor D. Quronov points out, it is essential to differentiate between literary theory and poetics [4]. V.M. Zhirmunsky wrote that poetics studies the system of expressive

means utilized by poetry [1]. Therefore, these specific linguistic units are studied precisely by linguopoetics. V. Vinogradov also stated that linguistic, aesthetic-stylistic, and literary approaches merge within the framework of poetics when analyzing the structure of a literary work [1]. According to A. Nurmonov, while linguistics studies the denotative meaning of language, literary studies examine its artistic-aesthetic function [3]. This aesthetic function of language constitutes the primary object of linguopoetics.

In Eastern philology, this issue is vividly reflected in Alisher Navoiy's *Muhakamat al-Lughatayn* (The Trial of the Two Languages). Navoiy examined the issues of word, meaning, and artistry within a unified philological framework [6]. Similarly, Abu Nasr al-Farabi distinguished the "science of poetry structure" as a separate branch, while Abdurauf Fitrat investigated how imagery is expressed through rhythm and sound (phonopoetics), offering initial insights into the artistic-aesthetic function of language [10].

Results and discussion

Linguopoetics provides literary studies with ready material for analyzing works of art. The linguist M. Yo'ldoshev emphasizes that although imagery is vital in literature, "there is no image without words" [11]. This view aligns with V.M. Zhirmunsky's assertion that "the material of poetry is not images, but words" [1]. R.A. Budagov notes that a writer's desire to exert an aesthetic impact on the reader endows language with an additional function— aesthetic power [12].

In Russian linguistics, R. Jakobson proposed viewing poetics as an integral part of linguistics, while N.M. Shansky argues that the analysis of a literary text must begin with linguistic analysis [13]. Scholars generally prefer the concept of "philological analysis" (i.e., linguopoetic analysis) for literary texts [14]. I. Mirzayev acknowledges that linguopoetics is currently the only field capable of restoring the severed integrity of philology [15]. As M. Yo'ldoshev aptly describes, when studying literary language, linguists and literary scholars must share a single, common philological blanket [11].

Conclusion

While philosophy, literature, and language issues were once unified in antiquity and later split into separate disciplines, modern linguopoetics reunites them into a single whole. The linguopoetic analysis of a literary work allows us to view the theoretical aspects of language, its social functions, and the reflection of human spirituality as an integrated entity. Ultimately, linguopoetics is a fundamental field that embodies various branches of philology and serves to restore its holistic nature.

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